

TEACHING ENGLISH TO KIDS THROUGH PICTURES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7902255>

Annotation. This article provides teaching English to kids by using interactive methods as well as ways to use different techniques and pictures during the lesson.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqola yosh bolalarga ingliz tilini interaktiv metodlar orqali o'rgatishni shuningdek, turli xil usullar, rasmlardan dars davomida samarali foydalanishni ko'rsatib o'tadi.

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается о преподавании английского языка детям с использованием интерактивных методов, а также о способах использования различных техник и картинок во время урока.

Key words: interactive, modern, cards, games, vocabulary.

After the independence of our motherland, great attention is paid to the study of foreign languages in our country. In particular, the decision of the first president of the Republic of Uzbekistan on further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages adopted on December 10, 2012 and the introduction of continuous teaching of foreign languages in the first grades of secondary schools since the academic year 2013-2014 are proof of this.

Nowadays, not only to students of schools, lyceums, collage and higher educational institutions, but also M. T. M. it is also established to teach foreign language, in particular English, to educators and employees working in various fields. There is a reason, of course. The study of the languages of economically, scientifically and culturally developed countries is the main factor in the acquisition of the achievements of World Science and development.

Language learning also depends on age periods. Psychologists believe that children acquire language more quickly and easily than adults. The natural predisposition to language learning in children, the fact that they have a strong mimicry characteristic, the abundance of children's time than in adults are the main reasons for this. It should be noted that children 6-7 years old do not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically.

Therefore, it is necessary not to start teaching English to primary school students with grammatical understanding. Otherwise, from the first step in

teaching a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and quench his interest. Therefore, teaching foreign language to young children is much more difficult and responsible. The following methods can be used to teach children English meaningfully and interestingly:

- to sing and teach letters or compounds that are difficult to explain or remember, without meaning, through songs and poems.

An example of this is to show that it is more effective for children to learn the English alphabet by singing than simply memorizing it.

- games that are articulated with mental and physical movements;

- cartoons; children seek to understand the words they are using, through the actions of cartoon characters, without understanding the statements in the cartoon during language learning. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn a language.

- role-playing (role play) the teacher must perform or perform some information through the role to children while teaching them, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: a pupil whining a dog, meowing a cat if it shows, it is necessary for another reader to know which animal these sounds belong to and say its English name.

thematic environment; children learn the language well if the teacher can create the same environment depending on the topic. For example: traveling, birthday, in the kitchen, etc. On the topic of Traveling (travel), the teacher will organize a trip, provide information on what means to go on a trip (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane), where it is important to travel (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, England, USA). This enhances the vocabulary, language capabilities of the students, cultivates the worldview.

- riddles; there is a strong interest in finding the answer to riddles in children. Therefore, if the teacher says the riddle in English or Uzbek, then his answer should require the children to say it in English. Then children learn words quickly.

- practical preoccupations (tasting fruits and other foods, sniffing flowers); this sentence can be explained by the opinions of a practicing psychologist: "an educator who wants something to be firmly entrenched in the memory of children should try to participate in the process of keeping as many of the child's sensory organs in mind as possible: the eye, ear, sound organ, muscle For example: when a teacher tastes an Apple, his color should be red (red) or green (green), the taste sweet (tasty) or sour, give information about the aroma, and, eating fruits to other students, he should demand that children give English

information about that fruit. This hoi also helps in the child's later learning. When the teacher asks the students for the English name of the colors, the child immediately remembers the moment when he ate the fruit, quickly remembers that it was red-red, green-green. Hence, the use of such a method ensures that the reader retains information in his memory in the long run.

-gestures, through facial expressions; it is understandable to the child when the teacher speaks or commands a sentence, for example, when he uses gestures in sentences such as Come On(come here), open the book(open the book), Stand Up(stand up), Look at the board(look at the blackboard).

- through visual weapons, posters, books;

- what is visible and used a lot in everyday life, to items

write. For example: door (door), Book(book), table(table), board (blackboard, write to Window(window) and so on. Such a thing is that the objects always fall into the eye and are used a lot in the amliothe, so the child learns these words in an involuntary way.

- through the news; we know that children are curious. They quickly get bored of the same. i therefore it is necessary to teach them not always to take lessons using one type of method, but I change such methods and take lessons by updating. Otherwise, the children will understand what kind of lesson the teacher will take and prepare for it. Updating the methods and taking lessons will increase the aspirations of children.

In conclusion, teaching language to younger children can be carried out in an interesting way of training, and not as an obligation, taking lessons using several effective methods can serve as a foundation for the knowledge they will receive in the future. How important it is for children to learn foreign languages is to be properly explained through natural conditions

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